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Effect of the nature of the liquid crystal on the phase separation kinetic behaviour in polymer/liquid crystal mixtures

Z.Hadjou Bélaïd^{1,*}, L.Méchèrnène¹, U. Maschke²,

¹ Tlemcen University, Faculty of sciences, Department of physics, PB 119 Rocade, Tlemcen, 13000, Algérie

² University of Sciences and Technologies of Lille.F-59655 Villeneuve d'Ascq Cedex, France

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ABSTRACT

Polymer Dispersed Liquid Crystals (PDLC) materials are generally prepared by a phase separation process induced by ultraviolet (UV) polymerization from a homogeneous mixture of pre-polymer and liquid crystal (LC). Phase separation kinetic was investigated by studying the evolution of the transmission over time of a film composed of a polymer/liquid crystal mixture. Two systems were considered: polyacrylate/E7 and polyacrylate/5CB. These mixtures consist of 30% by weight of Tripropylene glycoldiacrylate (TPGDA) and 70% by weight of LC, in the presence of 1% photoinitiator. Kinetics was studied by measuring, in the absence of external fields, the intensity of the light transmitted by the film before, during, and after irradiation of the films by UV light for different doses. Under UV light, the initial mixture (monomers/LC) will undergo polymerization-induced phase separation. One observes a rapid relaxation of the transmission at the beginning of the irradiation followed by an increase in the transmission for longer irradiation times. This surprising effect depends on the nature of LC as well as the distance between UV source and the sample.

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1. Introduction

Polymer/liquid crystal composite materials, called Polymer Dispersed Liquid Crystals (PDLC), are thin films with a polymer matrix structure in which liquid crystal microdroplets are dispersed [1, 2]. These materials are particularly interesting for their electro-optical applications in the field of display and variable opacity optical windows in particular [3, 4]. By applying an electric field to the PDLC film, the orientation of the liquid crystal molecules changes inside the droplets and, under certain conditions, the intensity of light transmitted by the film can vary between an opaque and a transparent state. These films are generally prepared by cross-linking polymerization under UV radiation, inducing phase separation between the polymer and the liquid crystal [7, 8]. The electro-optical performance of these materials depends crucially on many parameters such as the size and

* Corresponding author. Hadjou Bélaïd Zakia
E-mail address: z_hadjou@yahoo.fr

shape of the liquid crystal domains [5, 6]. These parameters are essentially controlled by the nature and conditions of the phase separation technique used in their development.

In this work, we are interested in quantifying and understanding the phenomenon of phase separation dynamics [8, 9] whose factors have a major effect on the morphology of these PDLC systems [11, 16]. Phase separation kinetics in most polymeric mixtures was actually a common and useful classical topic for the manufacture of heterogeneous composite materials [12]. Our systems are prepared under UV radiation inducing cross-linked polymerization of a monomer/liquid crystal mixture. A homogeneous solution of Tripropyleneglycoldiacrylate and a mixture of E7 nematic liquid crystal, once and 5CB another time, is prepared. The irradiation method using UV radiation, in the presence of Lucirin TPO [12, 14], was used to initiate the radical polymerization reaction of the monomer. During polymerization [15], liquid crystal molecules become less miscible with polymer chains whose lengths increase as polymerization progresses, and finally the mixture separates into two phases [17, 18], an isotropic polymer network and liquid crystal domains with morphologies dependent on irradiation conditions such as the nature of the UV source, its intensity and dose [19]. In this paper the phase separation kinetics of the mixture TPGDA/E7 and TPGDA/5CB was investigated to determine and analyze the different relaxing processes that accompany the formation of the PDLC system during polymerization and to find the influence of the nature of CL on this relaxation. This study, made by measuring the intensity of the transmitted light as a function of time before, during and after the application of UV light, allowed us to account for three phenomena: a rapid phase separation kinetics during which the transmission decreases, a reaugmentation of this transmission and finally a slow relaxation of the system after the UV lamp has been switched OFF.

2 Experimental part

2.1 Sample Preparation

The monomer used in this work is a monomer acrylate difonctionel TripropyleneGlycolDiAcrylate (TPGDA) (Figure 1) supplied by Gray Valley (France 1) with a molecular mass of 300.35g/mol and density of 1.03 g/mL. The first liquid crystal used here is the 4-Cyano-4'-n-pentyl-Biphenyl called (5CB), which has a temperature transition nematic-isotropic of 35.50 C and a positive dielectric anisotropy. The second is a commercial liquid crystal E7 (see Fig. 2) supplied by Merck KG Darmstadt which has an isotropic nematic transition temperature of 61°C. Initial mixtures are prepared for a single composition, 30 wt-%, TPGDA, 70 wt-% 5CB or E7 and 1wt-% (of polymer weight) photoprimer (Lucirin TPO, BASF) then placed in pillboxes that are left, under mechanical stirrer and at room temperature, for 12 hours until mixture homogeneity. A drop of this reactive mixture is then sandwiched between two very thin standard glass slats before being exposed to UV radiation. The PDLC film thickness was measured using a micrometer (Mitutovo; 1%µm uncertainty).

Figure 1. The chemical structure of the monomer TriproPyleneGlycolDiAcrylate (TPGDA).

Figure 2. The chemical structure of the nematic mixture E7

2.2 Experimental Methods

Ultraviolet light irradiation is done using a LC03 type UV irradiation source (from HAMAMATSU) equipped with a xenon lamp covering the spectrum between 250 and 800 nm, and an optical fiber (see Fig. 4). The samples were exposed to UV irradiation at a distance of 3.5cm between the optical fiber and the sample. The intensity of the light was kept constant at its higher level, and the exposure period of the samples was changed by 9.75s, 21.56s, 32.68s, 43s, 56s, and 60.06s using an automatic shutter.

Figure 3. Slide for measuring electro-optical properties.

Figure 4. UV irradiation lampe (LC03).

The light transmitted by the films is measured successively and continuously first for 20 seconds, the system is homogeneous and the transmission was 100%, then the system is irradiated at a period of exposure by UV light for a fixed time. We'll continue the transmission measurement until five minutes. The measurement of the transmission, repeated 3 times, is repeated after a pause of 30s to better account of the phenomenon of relaxation in the dark.

The light transmitted by the sample is detected by a photodiode whose raw data is processed by an operating system consisting of a microcomputer equipped with a DAC 1602 interface card. The distance between the photodiode and the sample is approximately 32cm and the reception angle of the UV beam (at the output of the optical fiber) with the sample in relation to the laser beam was 38° (see Fig. 3).

3. Results and discussions

We observe two relaxations, at the beginning a rapid relaxation after irradiation by UV light, which does not seem to depend on the dose of irradiation as shown in Figs 5 and 6. This relaxation is followed by an inverse effect where the transmission increases again (see Figs 5 (a) and (b)) was more important with increasing dose. This was thought to be a thermal effect, meaning that the sample heats up under the UV lamp and the system becomes isotropic again, so the transmission increases again [20, 21].

Figure 5. Irradiation time effect on TPGDA/5CB phase separation kinetics with a zoom of the descent.

Figure 6. Irradiation time effect on TPGDA/E7 phase separation kinetics with a zoom of the descent.

The effect of the nature of LC was illustrated in Figs. 7 and 8 (Fig. 7 for a UV dose equal to 9.75s and Fig. 8 for 60.06s) which show the evolution of transmission as a function of irradiation time for films of the same thickness, the same distance between the optical fiber and the sample and the same LC concentration.

Figure 7. Effect of LC nature on phase separation kinetics for irradiation time $t_{uv}=9.75s$ with zoom.

Figure 8. Effect of LC nature on phase separation kinetics for irradiation time $t_{uv}=60.06s$ with zoom.

Figs. 7 and 8 show that the relaxation of light transmission was highly dependent on the nature of the LC. It was observed that phase separation kinetics is faster for LC E7 (see Figs. 7 (b) and 8 (b)). However, the thermal effect is more important for the LC 5CB (see Fig.8 (a)). This is probably due to the fact that the 5CB at a nematic/isotropic temperature T_{NI} lower than that of E7 (see Fig. 8 (a)). The 5CB T_{ni} is close to ambient temperature. For this reason, a more important thermal effect is observed for this LC. The system in this case becomes isotropic, transparent, therefore a high transmittance. This gives unstable electrooptical properties for PDLC developed under these conditions and by these constituents.

The LC 5CB has a lower diffusion coefficient than E7 (0.22 for E7 and 0.143 for 5CB). Hence, the relaxation of LC 5CB molecules inside the polymer matrix under UV radiation was no longer the same. The molecules of the liquid crystal, have the property of being oriented in a single privileged direction. The 5CB at a diffusion coefficient lower than that of E7 which brings a slow relaxation of these molecules.

4. Conclusion

In this work we carried out a study of phase separation kinetics in PDLC systems which provided us with important information on the behaviour of phase separation in relation to various crucial parameters such as radiation dose, the nature and concentration of the LC in particular. This study to show that the rapid relaxation which follows the beginning of the irradiation does not depend on the concentration in LC but depends on its nature. We have also shown that the thermal effect which depends on the UV dose, concentration in LC, and its nature. The thermal effect was greater in the case of 5CB; this is probably due to the fact that the isotropic nematic transition temperature T_{NI} of the latter was lower which leads it into an isotropic state for more basic temperatures hence the increase in transmission.

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